

Phase shifts due to IFOV depointing

L Lindegren 1985 Oct 29

This effect is most pronounced when the star image is slightly out of focus on the main grid, simultaneously with a significant defocussing on the photocathode. CIP run #20 (letter to E Zeis 1984-12-19) gives results for a typical (?) case, viz.

telescope defocus = 15 μm
relay optics def. = 150 μm
IFOV diameter = 110 μm

(no other aberrations included). The following approximate relations were derived for the phase shifts in radians, as functions of the depointing (Δw , Δz):

$$d_1 = 4.6 \cdot 10^{-5} (\Delta w/1'')^3 [1 + (r/23'')^6]^{-1}$$

$$d_2 = 0.6 d_1$$

where $r = \sqrt{(\Delta w)^2 + (\Delta z)^2}$ is the total depointing. The maximum shift of the first harmonic is $d_1 = \pm 0.28$ rad (54 mas) at $w = \pm 23''$, $z = 0$. At the same point the shift of the second harmonic is a maximum $d_2 = \pm 0.17$ rad (16 mas). The effects of these shifts on the Fourier coefficients b_1 to b_5 can be approximated as

$$\Delta b_1 = 0$$

$$\Delta b_2 \approx -d_1 b_3$$

$$\Delta b_3 \approx +d_1 b_2$$

$$\Delta b_4 \approx -d_2 b_5$$

$$\Delta b_5 \approx +d_2 b_4$$

